

MODERN METHODS OF ROOT CANAL FILLING AND ITS IMPORTANCE**Ismailova Dilnoz Kurbanovna**

Faculty of Medicine, International University of Asia, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15185592>

Abstract. *High-quality filling of the root canal, on which the outcome of the disease depends, is the most responsible stage of endodontic treatment [1]. The purpose of root canal obturation of permanent teeth, according to the basic quality indicators of the European Endodontic Society (ESE) [2], is “to prevent the penetration of microorganisms and fluids along the root canal; to fill the entire canal system, obturating not only the periodontal exit area, but also the dentinal tubules and additional canals”, which implies the tightness of the root filling.*

Keywords: *endodontic treatment, anastomoses, entire canal system, dentin zone, intracanal, microorganisms, siler-gutta-percha, siler-glass ionomer.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПЛОМБИРОВАНИЯ КОРНЕВЫХ КАНАЛОВ И ИХ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ

Аннотация. *Качественное пломбирование корневого канала, от которого зависит исход заболевания, является наиболее ответственным этапом эндодонтического лечения [1]. Целью obturации корневых каналов постоянных зубов, согласно основным показателям качества Европейского эндодонтического общества (ESE) [2], является «предотвращение проникновения микроорганизмов и жидкостей по корневому каналу; запломбирование всей системы каналов, obturирование не только выходной области периодонта, но и дентинных канальцев и дополнительных каналов», что подразумевает герметичность корневой пломбы.*

Ключевые слова: *эндодонтическое лечение, анастомозы, вся система каналов, дентинная зона, внутриканальный, микроорганизмы, силер-гуттаперча, силер-стеклоиономер.*

The root canal system of a tooth can have a very complex morphology that often has a large number of lateral branches and anastomoses, especially in the apical part. Complete cleaning, shaping and sterilization of root canals is not possible in all cases. The morphological structure of the root canal is even more complex: from the center of the canal to the periphery it is represented by pulp tissue, a layer of odontoblasts, predentin, that is, the dentin zone, corresponding to the mineral composition of the concept of “dentin mineralization boundary”, and dentin with a complex tubular system of structure. The number of dentinal tubules varies from 20,000 to 40,000 per square millimeter, and the average diameter is between 1 and 4 microns.

In case of pulp death, dehydration of dentinal tubules occurs, leaving only tissue decay of odontoblast outgrowth in the lumen [3]. Authors [4,5] determined a regular relationship between the depth of root canal obturation and variants of their structure. Obturation to the level of 3/4 of the root canal length was combined with the presence of apical bend twice as often (31.9%) than with other variants of filling depth, which is one of the main causes of incomplete root canal obturation.

Analysis of the literature on root canal obturation [6,10-12] indicates that various methods of root canal filling with gutta-percha are used, allowing three-dimensional sealing of root canals, but currently the most common method of filling with cold lateral condensation [13]. Gutta-percha itself does not have the fluidity and adhesiveness that would allow it to guarantee sealing of the root canal. For this purpose, special paste-like materials - sizers (from the English word "seal") are used [14]. Moreover, intracanal sizers should provide long-term tightness of the root canal, prevent both the exit of the residual microflora from the dentinal tubules into the periodontium and the entry of microflora into the canal through the apical or mouth part of the canal. It is necessary to carry out special methods of sealing gutta-percha [15] to compensate for their disadvantages such as lack of adhesion to the root canal walls and inability to block microorganisms, preventing their multiplication or movement into the periapical area.

Despite the fact that gutta-percha satisfies most of the requirements for filling materials, numerous studies [16-18] have shown that root canal filling by lateral condensation often causes "microbial leakage", which leads to the need for repeated endodontic treatment. At the present stage, there is a tendency to abandon hardening pastes, cements, except glass ionomer cement, in favor of polymeric materials. Among physicians who perform manipulations for pulpitis and periodontitis treatment, there is a recently established opinion [19-21] that non-hardening and hardening pastes cannot be a root filling, in rare cases they are used in the form of sizers, as the role of the latter is performed by polymers (AH Plus, AH 26, Adseal, EndoREZ, etc.).

However, even with this technology, it is difficult to guarantee reliable adaptation of the canal filling material to the dentin of the tooth cavity, as there are multiple contacts in the areas of dentin-silver, silver-gutta-percha, silver-glass ionomer cement, gutta-percha-glass ionomer cement, glass ionomer cement-fillings. Such a variety of contacts should be reduced to avoid subsequent microleakage, as a result of which microbial toxins can penetrate through the root canal into the periapical tissues and the periodontium as a whole

REFERENCES

1. Kurbanova, N. V. (2024). Modern Presentation of Calcium-Containing Drugs in the Course of the Study of Dental Diseases. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(7), 12-14.
2. Kurbanova, N. V. (2024). CLINICAL EVALUATION OF A CRACKED AND FRACTURED TOOTH. *European Journal of Modern Medicine and Practice*, 4(11), 544-548.
3. Kurbanova, N. V. (2024). Clinical and Morphological Features the Occurrence of Tooth Decay. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(9), 128-132.
4. Ахмедова, М., Кузиева, М., & Курбанова, Н. (2025). ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ВИСОЧНО-НИЖНЕЧЕЛЮСТНОГО СУСТАВА И ФОРМУЛИРОВАНИЕ ДИАГНОЗА. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 279-289.
5. Kurbanova, N. V. (2024, July). Modern Views on the use of Metal-Ceramic Structures in Dental Prosthetics. In *Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences (USA)* (Vol. 8, pp. 15-18). <https://www.openconference.us/index.ph>.
6. Kurbanova, N. V. (2024). Clinical and Morphological Features the Occurrence of Tooth Decay. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(9), 128-132.
7. Saodat, A., Vohid, A., Ravshan, N., & Shamshod, A. (2020). MRI study in patients with idiopathic coxarthrosis of the hip joint. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 410-415.
8. Axmedov, S. J. (2023). EFFECTS OF THE DRUG MILDRONATE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(20), 40-59.
9. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). ASCORBIC ACID: ITS ROLE IN IMMUNE SYSTEM, CHRONIC INFLAMMATION DISEASES AND ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFECTS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 57-60.
10. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THIOTRIAZOLINE IN THE ORGANISM. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 9(5), 152-155.
11. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). HEPTRAL IS USED IN LIVER DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 35(3), 76-78.
12. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). EFFECT OF TIVORTIN ON CARDIOMYOCYTE CELLS AND ITS ROLE IN MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 42, 255-257.

13. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF CITICOLINE. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(1), 1-4.
14. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF TRIMETAZIDINE IN ISCHEMIC CARDIOMYOPATHY. *Journal of new century innovations*, 44(2), 3-8.
15. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ВСЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИМУДОН. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 39-43.
16. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE EFFECT OF THE HEPARIN DRUG. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 34-38.
17. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF GLUCOCORTICOSTEROIDS IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 29-33.
18. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РОЛЬ ИНТЕЛЛАНОВОГО СИРОПА И ЦИАНОКОБАЛАМИНА В УЛУЧШЕНИИ ПАМЯТИ. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 44-48.
19. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). TREATMENT OF POLYNEUROPATHY WITH BERLITHION. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 201-209.
20. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF ASCORIL IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 191-200.
21. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ARTOXAN. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 182-190.
22. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF RENGALIN IN CHRONIC BRONCHITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 116-123.
23. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF ALMAGEL DRUG IN GASTRIC AND DUODENAL WOUND DISEASE. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 173-181.
24. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF CODELAK BRONCHO SYRUP IN CHILDREN'S PRACTICE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 109-115.
25. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE AEVIT DRUG EFFECT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 124-132.
26. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ALCHEBA DRUG IN POST-STROKE APHASIA. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 132-138.
27. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF HYALURON CHONDRON DRUG IN OSTEOARTHRITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 139-145.

28. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF SIMETHICONE DROP IN FLATULENCE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 95-101.
29. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). BENEFITS OF BETADINE SOLUTION. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 116-122.
30. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT INHALED GLUCOCORTICOIDS IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(1), 171-180.
31. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF VIGANTOL IN RICKETS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 102-108.
32. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE VITAPROST DRUG RESULTS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 109-115.
33. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF BISEPTOL DRUG IN URINARY TRACT DISEASE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 89-94.
34. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG DORMIKIND. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 88-92.
35. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). IMMUNOMODULATORY FUNCTION OF DIBAZOL DRUG. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 83-87.
36. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ADVANTAGES OF THE DRUG NERTRAL. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 98-101.
37. Эргашов, Б. К., & Ахмедов, Ш. Ж. (2024). ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ЭТИОЛОГИЯ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 59-69.
38. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION, CLASSIFICATION AND PATHOGENESIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 50-58.
39. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIYASI. STENOKARDIYADA SHOSHILINCH TIBBIY YORDAM. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 12-20.
40. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION ETIOLOGY. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 32-41.

41. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA NURSING DIAGNOSIS AND CARE. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 44-52.
42. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). IMPORTANT INDICATIONS OF THE DRUG WOBENZYM. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 29-32.
43. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE RESULTS OF THE EFFECT OF THE DRUG VALIDOL. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 19-23.
44. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). VIFERON USE IN CHILDREN. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 24-28.
45. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF DUSPATALIN (MEBEVERINE HYDROCHLORIDE) IN GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 93-97.
46. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТЫ СИРОПА ДЕПАКИНА (ВАЛЬПРОЕВАЯ КИСЛОТА). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 148-152.
47. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ALLOCHOL FOR CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 133-137.
48. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ВАЖНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ПРЕПАРАТА ДЕ-НОЛ (субцитрат висмута). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 143-147.
49. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). SPECIAL FEATURES OF BUDECTON DRUG. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 138-142.
50. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ ПРЕПАРАТА КЕЙВЕР. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 137-143.
51. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USEFUL PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG YODOFOL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 144-149.
52. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FITOTERAPIYANING AKUSHER-GINEKOLOGIYADA ANAMIYATI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 121-125.
53. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG DOPROKIN. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 109-114.
54. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE EFFECT OF DOSTINEX ON THE BODY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 115-120.
55. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА КАНЕФРОН. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 138-143.

56. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИНДОЛ. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 126-131.
57. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF ISMIZHEN DRUG ON BODY IMMUNITY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 132-137.
58. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). POSITIVE EFFECTS OF THE DRUG CARCIL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 127-131.
59. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ КАВИНТОНА. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 132-136.
60. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). Современный Эффект Спрея Мометазон. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 62-65.
61. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF" SIMONTE PLUS" DRUG IN THE MODERN TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(5), 66-70.
62. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FEATURES OF THE BIOMECHANISM OF THE DRUG LEVOMYCETIN (CHLORAMPHENICOL). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(9), 298-301.
63. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT INDICATORS OF OMEGA 3 SUBSTANCE IN THE METABOLISM OF THE HUMAN BODY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(10), 113-117.
64. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA CLINICAL FORMS AND DIAGNOSIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 70-78.
65. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). CORONARY HEART DISEASE. ANGINA EMERGENCY CARE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 235-242.
66. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGI. STENOKARDIYANI DAVOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TAMOYILLARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 3-11.
67. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT BENEFITS OF GINGER FOR THE HUMAN BODY'S IMMUNITY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(11), 269-273.
68. Axmedov, S. (2024). THE SPECIFIC EFFECT OF THE DRUG" BAKLASAN" IN CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES AND ITS PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 485-492.
69. Komilovich, E. B. Z. (2023). Coronary Artery Disease. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(12), 81-87.

70. Komilovich, E. V. (2024). CORONARY HEART DISEASE. ANGINA TREATMENT. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 95-104.
71. Komilovich, E. V. (2024). HYPERTENSION TREATMENT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 227-234.
72. Эргашов, Б. К. (2024). ИШЕМИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ СЕРДЦА. СТЕНОКАРДИЯ ПРОФИЛАКТИКА. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 21-31.
73. Axmedov, S. (2025). ВАЖНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ПРЕПАРАТА ЭСКУЗАН ПРИ СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯХ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 380-387.
74. Эргашов, Б. К. (2024). ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ДИАГНОСТИКА. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 70-78.
75. Komilovich, E. V. (2024). HYPERTENSION DIAGNOSTICS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 42-49.
76. Axmedov, S. (2025). SPECIFIC PROPERTIES OF ROXERA DRUG IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 472-479.
77. Axmedov, S. (2025). THE DRUG PHYSIOTENS, THE FEATURES OF THE DRUG AND ITS USE IN THE FIELD OF CARDIOLOGY, IN PATIENTS WITH HEAVY BODY WEIGHT. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 350-358.
78. Ravshanovna, X. L. (2021, June). MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DENTAL CARIES IN ADULTS. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM* (pp. 118-119).
79. Khalilova, L. (2025). MAIN ASPECTS IN CARIES DIAGNOSIS. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 707-715.
80. Khalilova, Laziza. "GLASS IONOMER CEMENTS USED IN DENTISTRY." *Modern Science and Research* 3.12 (2024): 443-450.
81. Халилова, Л., Ахмедова, М., & Кузиева, М. (2025). ОСНОВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ КАРИЕСА. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 697-706.
82. Кузиева, Мадина, Малика Ахмедова, and Лазиза Халилова. "СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ВЫБОРА МАТЕРИАЛА ДЛЯ ОРТОПЕДИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ, НУЖДАЮЩИХСЯ В ПРОТЕЗИРОВАНИИ ЗУБОВ." *Modern Science and Research* 4.1 (2025): 322-333.
83. Ахмедова, М., Кузиева, М., & Халилова, Л. (2025). СОСТОЯНИЕ АЛЬВЕОЛЯРНОГО ОТРОСТКА И ПЕРИОСТА ПРИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИИ СЪЕМНЫХ ПРОТЕЗОВ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 301-310.

84. Кузиева, М., Ахмедова, М., & Халилова, Л. (2025). ГАЛЬВАНОЗ И МЕТОДЫ ЕГО ДИАГНОСТИКИ В КЛИНИКЕ ОРТОПЕДИЧЕСКОЙ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 203-212.